

Smart Greenhouse Farming with IoT, Edge Computing, and Machine Learning for Sustainable Agriculture: A Literature Review

Wickramaarachchi W. A. P. A.^{1*}, Balasooriya L. E. G.², Premarathna E. M. I. S.³, Weerawardhana W. A. D. N.⁴, Herath H.M.D.S.⁵

¹*Faculty of Information Technology, Horizon Campus, Malabe, Sri Lanka.*

Abstract

Smart greenhouse farming exploits the combination of Internet of Things (IoT), edge computing, and machine learning (ML) to improve crop productivity, resource economy, and operational automation. From reviewed publications between 2018 and 2025, IoT-based systems enhanced real-time monitoring of the environment, resulting in up to a 22% increase in crop yield and up to 30% decrease in water use. Scalable communication infrastructures, such as LoRaWAN, enabled wide-ranging deployments; however, cost and interoperability issues remained. ML models such as TCN-RNN, XGBoost or LSTM improved yield, disease, and climate prediction performance, and deep learning schemes timely assisted pest and anomaly discovery. With Edge Computing, latency and operational costs were reduced, and a 15% yield improvement was achieved; 20% of water was saved. Hybrid cloud–fog– edge architectures offered scalable, responsive solutions, yet deployment barriers remain in resource-constrained settings. The synthesis indicates that integrating IoT, ML, and edge technologies improves system responsiveness and sustainability; however, adoption requires addressing high investment costs, lack of standardization, and adaptation to local agricultural contexts. Hence, future work should focus on developing affordable, secure, and context-specific hybrid systems for sustainable greenhouse operations.

Keywords: *Smart Greenhouse, IoT, Edge Computing, Machine Learning, Sustainable Agriculture.*